

Effectiveness of bladder control training package among children diagnosed with enuresis in selected community areas of city

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Abstract

Enuresis, also known as bedwetting, is a distressing illness that primarily affects young children. It is the involuntary night-time loss of pee that is not brought on by an underlying illness. Social issues, bullying by siblings, and low self-esteem might arise from it. It affects up to 2% of young adults and 15 to 20% of five-year-olds. The goal of the study was to assess Effectiveness of bladder control training package among children diagnosed with enuresis in selected community areas of city.

Objective: To assess the effectiveness of bladder control training package among children diagnosed with enuresis in selected community areas of city.

Methodology:

The researcher used a quantitative research approach in the present study to assess the effectiveness of bladder control training package among children diagnosed with enuresis in selected community areas of city. This research employed a pre experimental research design which was a non-randomized one-group pre-test and post-test design. The sampling technique used was the non-probability purposive sampling technique. The setting was a selected community areas of city. The research was carried out among 30 children age between 7 to 10 years in selected in community areas of city, by using a non-probability purposive sampling technique. The information was gathered using a demographic characteristics and self-structured observational checklist. The scores were classified as Slight enuresis (score 0- 1), Mild enuresis (score 2- 3), Moderate enuresis (score 4 - 5), Data collection is the process of recruiting participants and gathering information for a research. Administrative approval was acquired in writing. To ensure a truthful answer, the chosen participants were informed about the objective and use of the research and ensured of the anonymity of their replies. Each participant in the research provided written informed permission.

Result:

The analysis of the study was done using descriptive and inferential statistics. The master sheet was prepared and coding of the responses was done. The data was presented in the form of tables and charts. Statistics were performed with the help of paired t-tests and fisher's tests.

The results indicate that average enuresis score in the pre-test was 4.2, which was reduced to 3.8 in the post-test. T-value for this test was 3.8 with 29 degrees of freedom. The corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), and the null hypothesis is rejected. It is evident that the bladder control training program is significantly effective in reducing enuresis among children.

KEY WORDS: effectiveness, bladder control training package, enuresis in children.

INTRODUCTION

The field of paediatrics in medicine is concerned with the health and well-being of children from conception to puberty. The specialty area of nursing practice known as paediatric nursing, focuses on the treatment of children in both healthy and sick conditions. It covers preventive, promotional, curative, and rehabilitative child care. The goal of paediatric nursing is to enable each growing and developing child to reach their potential and function to the best of their abilities. Understanding children's developmental stages as well as the physical and psychological distinctions between children and adults is essential for paediatric nurses.

Enuresis affects people of all ethnicities and civilisations globally. It is a prevalent issue among school-age children, with varying studies reporting different prevalence rates. Often, these contradictions are the result of unclear definitions. The cause of enuresis is unknown, although potential causes include stress, inadequate toilet training, heredity, sleep arousal disorder, maturational delay, altered smooth-muscle physiology, and occasionally pathological causes. Although bedwetting can be diagnosed in children as young as five years old, it is typically not treated clinically until the children are seven or eight years old.

A 2024 study investigated the clinic-epidemiological profile of children presenting with enuresis in India. The study found that enuresis prevalence was highest among children aged 5 to 7 years, accounting for 73.4% of cases, with a decrease in prevalence as age increased. The majority of cases were non-monosymptomatic, with overactive bladder being the most common associated condition.

BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Enuresis affects people of all ethnicities and civilisations globally. It is a prevalent issue among school-age children, with varying studies reporting different prevalence rates. Often, these contradictions are the result of unclear definitions. The cause of enuresis is unknown, although potential causes include stress, inadequate toilet training, heredity, sleep arousal disorder, maturational delay, altered smooth-muscle physiology, and occasionally pathological causes. Although bedwetting can be diagnosed in children as young as five years old, it is typically not treated clinically until the children are seven or eight years old.

Bedwetting or enuresis, is a prevalent but poorly treated paediatric illness. Enuresis (bedwetting) affects up to 20% of five-year-olds and can have considerable social, emotional, and psychological effects. Treatments include alarms (activated by urination), behavioural interventions, and drugs. Although many published papers offer guidance on the clinical assessment and treatment of enuresis, no systematic evaluation of their methodological soundness has been done. Comprehensive training programs that combine physiological interventions with behavioural and educational strategies show promise in helping children achieve and maintain bladder control. However, ongoing support and tailored approaches are essential to maximize long-term success and minimize the psychological effects of the condition

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5 to 7 years, accounting for 73.4% of cases, with a decrease in prevalence as age increased. The majority of cases were non-monosymptomatic, with overactive bladder being the most common associated condition. Enuresis (or nocturnal enuresis) is the involuntary loss of urine at night, in the absence of organic disease, at an age when a child could reasonably be expected to be dry (by consensus, at a developmental age of five years).

The International Children's Continence Society (ICCS) promotes the use of standardised nomenclature for describing paediatric lower urinary tract function, particularly in research, so that studies can be compared with improved understanding about the pathophysiology of bedwetting, enuresis is now sub classified as either monosymptomatic (bedwetting only) or non-monosymptomatic (bedwetting with lower urinary tract symptoms in the presence or absence of daytime urinary incontinence). This sub classification is important, as the pathophysiology and treatment for both are different. However, many older studies did not distinguish between these groups. The ICCS has also defined treatment outcomes in terms of change in frequency of wetting compared with baseline frequency (non-response is less than a 50% reduction in frequency of wetting, partial response is 50% to 99% reduction and complete response is 100% reduction), relapse (more than one symptom recurrence a month after cessation of treatment) and duration of treatment success (initial success is a complete response at the end of treatment, continued success is a complete response for six months after cessation of treatment, and complete success is a complete response for two years after cessation of treatment). Unfortunately, most older studies usually did not assess these outcomes or were unclear about their definition of success.¹²

METHODOLOGY

The current research was designed to assess the Effectiveness of bladder control training package among children diagnosed with enuresis in selected community areas of city. This research employed a pre experimental research design as well as Pre-experimental, non-randomized one-group pre-test and post-test design. The research was carried out among 30 children age between 7 to 10 years in selected in community areas of city, by using a non-probability purposive sampling technique. The information was gathered using a demographic characteristics and self-structured observational checklist. The scores were classified as Slight enuresis (score 0- 1), Mild enuresis (score 2- 3), Moderate enuresis (score 4 - 5), Data collection is the process of recruiting participants and gathering information for a research. Administrative approval was acquired in writing. To ensure a truthful answer, the chosen participants were informed about the objective and use of the research and ensured of the anonymity of their replies. Each participant in the research provided written informed permission.

DESCRIPTION OF THE INTERVENTION

- a. First, the investigator established a good rapport with the parents and introduced the study topic to the parents and child of enuresis. The investigator took the assent from the parents. The investigator collected the data regarding demographic variables.
- b. The investigator assessed the selected signs and symptoms before performing bladder control, alarm method and Kegel exercises.
- c. The investigator explained the procedure of the bladder training package to the parents and child.

- d. The included bladder control, alarm method and Kegel exercises (meaning, importance, precautions and description of each exercise) and will give intervention for 15 days.
- e. Investigator demonstrated the steps of bladder control, alarm method and Kegel exercise. Also told them to remonstrate with it. Bladder control training is instructed to be performed twice a day, in the morning and evening.
- f. Alarm method is to be performed during night-time at once and Kegel exercises two times a day, in the morning and evening.
- g. The investigator demonstrated and gave information about the intervention on the first day to parents/caregivers and the child. The investigator took follow-up for 3 days and filled out the self-directed checklist either physically. After that investigator took follow-up telephonically till the 15th day and filled the checklist.

After the end of the intervention assessment of selected signs and symptoms is conducted using by self-directed checklist on the 15th day

RESULTS

SECTION I

Description of samples based on their demographic characteristics.

Age

In this study, 43.3% of the children diagnosed with enuresis were aged 7-8 years, 23.3% of them were aged 8-9 years, and 33.3% of them were aged 9-10 years.

Gender

The study showed that 66.7% of them were males and 33.3% of them were females.

Family history of enuresis

In this study 33.3% of them had a family history of enuresis.

Parental Education

In this study, 10% of their parents had 10th standard education, 56.7% of them had 12th standard education, and 33.3% of them were graduates.

Child Care Taker

In this study, 73.3% of their caretakers were their mothers, 20% of them had foster parents as caretakers and 6.7% of them had other relatives to take care of them.

Type of enuresis

56.7% of them had nocturnal enuresis, 10% of them had diurnal enuresis and 33.3% of them had mixed enuresis.

Frequency of bed wetting

The study showed that 60% of them had bed wetting once and 40% of them had bed wetting twice.

SECTION II

Analysis of data related to pre-assessment of children diagnosed with enuresis

N=30

Enuresis	Pretest		Posttest	
	Freq	%	Freq	%
Slight	0	0.0%	0	0.0%
Mild	5	16.7%	13	43.3%
Moderate	25	83.3%	17	56.7%

Bar diagram showing percentage-wise distribution of samples according to pre-assessment of the children diagnosed with enuresis

The above table and bar graph show that 16.7% of the children diagnosed with enuresis had mild enuresis and 83.3% of them had moderate enuresis.

SECTION III

Analysis of data related to the effect of bladder control training among children diagnosed with enuresis in selected community areas of city.

N=30

Enuresis	Pre-test		Post-test	
	Freq	%	Freq	%
Slight	0	0.0%	0	0.0%
Mild	5	16.7%	13	43.3%
Moderate	25	83.3%	17	56.7%

Bar diagram showing percentage-wise distribution effect of bladder control training package among children diagnosed with enuresis in selected community areas of city

The above table and the bar graph shows that, pre-test, 16.7% of the children diagnosed with enuresis had mild enuresis and 83.3% of them had moderate enuresis. In the post-test, 43.3% of them had mild enuresis and 56.7% of them had moderate enuresis. This indicates that there is a remarkable improvement in enuresis among children after bladder control training.

Paired t-test for the effect of bladder control training among children diagnosed with enuresis in selected community areas of city

N=30

	Mean	SD	t	df	p-value
Pre-test	4.2	0.7	3.8	29	0.000
Post-test	3.8	0.9			

Graph

Bar diagram showing the average enuresis score among children diagnosed with enuresis in pre-test and post-test

The above table and bar graph show that the researcher applied a paired t-test for the effect of bladder control training among children diagnosed with enuresis in selected community areas of city. The average enuresis score in the pre-test was 4.2, which was reduced to 3.8 in the post-test. T-value for this test was 3.8 with 29 degrees of freedom. The corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), and the null hypothesis is rejected. It is evident that the bladder control training program is significantly effective in reducing enuresis among children.

Comparison between pre-test and post-test

N=30

Enuresis	Pre-test		Post-tests	
	Freq	%	Freq	%
Bed wetting	30	100.0%	30	100.0%
Dribbling of urine	19	63.3%	17	56.7%
Tightly crossing legs	30	100.0%	29	96.7%
Snoring	18	60.0%	14	46.7%
Restless	30	100.0%	24	80.0%

Graph**Line diagram showing comparison between pre-test and post-test**

The above table and line graph show that, in the pre-test and posttest, all of the children diagnosed with enuresis had bed wetting. In pre-test, 63.3% of them had dribbling urine and in posttest, 56.7% of them had dribbling of urine. In pre-test, 100% had symptoms of tightly crossing legs and in posttest, 96.7% of them had tightly crossing legs. In pre-test, 60% of them were snoring and 46.7% of them in the posttest were snoring. In the pre-test, 100% were restless and in the posttest 80% of them were restless.

Section IV

Analysis of data related to the association between selected demographic variables and enuresis.

Fisher's exact test for the association between selected demographic variables and enuresis.

Demographic variable		Enuresis		p-value
		Mild	Moderate	
Age	7-8 years	3	10	0.572
	8-9 years	0	7	
	9-10 years	2	8	
Gender	Male	4	16	0.640
	Female	1	9	
Family history of enuresis	Yes	2	8	1.000
	No	3	17	
Parental Education	10th standard	1	2	0.138
	12th Standard	1	16	
	Graduate	3	7	
Child Care Taker	Mother	3	19	0.507
	Foster parents	2	4	
	Other relatives	0	2	
Type of enuresis	Nocturnal	3	14	0.618
	Diurnal	1	2	
	Mixed	1	9	
Frequency of bed wetting	One time	5	13	0.066
	Two times	0	12	

All the p-values were large (greater than 0.05), and none of the demographic variables was found to have a significant association with the enuresis.

DISCUSSION

This study evaluated the effectiveness of a bladder control training package among children with enuresis in selected community areas. A pre-experimental one-group pre-test post-test design was used with 30 purposively selected children. Data were collected using a validated and reliable checklist, and ethical clearance was obtained. A pilot study confirmed the feasibility of the research.

The average enuresis score decreased from 4.2 (pre-test) to 3.8 (post-test). The paired t-test result ($t = 3.8, p < 0.05$) showed a statistically significant improvement, indicating that the training program was effective. The findings support that bladder control training can help reduce enuresis in children.

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CONCLUSION

This study concludes that the bladder control training package was effective in improving bladder control among children with enuresis in selected community areas. A significant difference was observed between pre-test and post-test scores, indicating the positive impact of the intervention. Thus, bladder control training can be considered a beneficial, community-based nursing intervention to reduce enuresis among children

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